

MONETARY POLICY IN THE CONDITIONS OF CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC

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Abstract

The Koronavirus pandemic has led to a sharp decline in the solvency of companies, deepening the liquidity problem in commercial banks, and an increase in the inflation of the money supply. It highlights the need for correction of monetary policy and the increase of its role in mitigating the effects of the pandemic.

The article provides an opportunity to improve the monetary policy of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan during the coronavirus pandemic.

Keyword: coronavirus pandemic, monetary policy, liquidity, currency, commercial banks, foreign currency

The coronavirus pandemic has made a strong negative impact on the national economy of Uzbekistan. In particular, the cash flow of pandemic-affected entities has weakened, the probability of non-repayment or overdue payment of loans extended by commercial banks has increased, and the national currency has depreciated as a result of declining foreign exchange supply. This fact necessitates reconsidering the role of the monetary policy in the conditions of the pandemic. In this regard, investigating the impact of reserve requirements and monetary policy on the activities of commercial

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banks, which are traditional instruments of monetary policy, assessing the practice of controlling the money supply growth, studying possibility of ensuring the stability of national exchange rates are considered crucially important in mitigating negative consequences of a pandemic.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №PD-5978 “On additional measures to support the population, sectors of the economy and businesses during the coronavirus pandemic” dated April 3, 2020 is aimed at support of strategic enterprises through the allocation of three-year budget loans for the implementation of primary expenses, reimbursement of part of the transportation costs of foreign trade entities, support of commercial banks in the event of deterioration in the quality of loan portfolios¹.

It should be noted that one of the measures to combat the coronavirus pandemic is to provide lending (repayment) holidays to the population and businesses. According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №PD-5969 “On priority measures to mitigate the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic and the global crisis on economic sectors” dated March 19, 2020, the payments of loans by legal entities and individuals facing financial difficulties on repaying the loans by commercial banks, have been postponed until October 1, 2020². This makes a strong negative impact on the liquidity of commercial banks. This is due to the fact that according to the Decree, the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan is to provide liquidity in the amount of 2.0 trillion UZS to commercial banks for a three-year period. However, the amount of overdue loans of commercial banks amounted to 19.6 trillion UZS. From which financial source will the rest of the unbalanced liquidity in banks be replenished? This issue is still under consideration.

One of the most pressing issues of monetary policy within the framework of the coronavirus pandemic is the policy of reserve requirements. The Central Bank’s policy

¹ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №PD-5978 “On additional measures to support the population, sectors of the economy and businesses during the coronavirus pandemic” dated April 3, 2020 //www.cbu.uz.

² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan №PD-5969 “On priority measures to mitigate the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic and the global crisis on economic sectors” dated March 19, 2020//www.cbu.uz.

of reserve requirements makes a direct and strong impact on the liquidity of commercial banks. Therefore, in the current context of serious risks to the liquidity of commercial banks, it is necessary to raise the role of incentives of policy of reserve requirements.

Starting from October 1, 2018, the procedure for the formation of required reserves only in the national currency was introduced, the reserve requirements for foreign currency deposits were increased and set at the rate of 14%.³

Another topical issue of monetary policy is to ensure stability of the nominal exchange rate of the national currency. This is due to the fact that a significant decrease in the nominal exchange rate of the national currency, i.e. a high rate of its devaluation, results in negative devaluation expectations of the population and businesses. As a result, the demand for foreign currency will rise sharply, or in other words, “dollar fetishism” will increase. On September 5, 2017, due to the liberalization of the exchange rate policy, the nominal exchange rate of the national currency - the UZS against the USD fell by almost half, i.e. the national currency depreciated twice: the value of 1 USD in UZS increased from 4210.00 UZS up to 8100.00 UZS. However, we could not keep this exchange rate either. On April 16, 2020 the nominal exchange rate of the national currency against 1 USD constituted 10121.00 UZS.

Ensuring low and stable interest rates on loans extended by commercial banks is one of the key issues of the monetary policy of the Central Bank of Uzbekistan.

The data illustrated in Table 1 show that the inflation rate in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2021 is declining. This allowed the Central Bank to reduce the refinancing rate during this period. In turn, the reduction of the Central Bank’s refinancing rate resulted in the decrease in interest rates on loans of commercial banks in the national currency.

³ Report on the activities of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018 //www.cbu.uz.

Table 1

Annual inflation rate in the Republic of Uzbekistan, annual interest rate of the Central Bank refinancing rate and average annual interest rate on loans of commercial banks in the national currency, in percent⁴

Indicators	2019	2020	2021
Inflation rate	15,2	11,1	10,0
Refinancing rate	16,0	14,0	14,0
Interest rate on loans extended by commercial banks	24,2	22,3	20,8

The data in Table 1 show that the interest rate on loans issued by commercial banks of the republic in the national currency in 2019-2021 was high. This will prevent legal entities and individuals from increasing their access to loans extended by commercial banks.

In order to increase the role of monetary policy in mitigating the negative impact of the pandemic under conditions of the coronavirus pandemic, it is advisable to implement the following measures:

1. To eliminate the negative impact of the Central Bank’s reserve requirements on the liquidity of commercial banks and the strength of the resource base, first, it is necessary to abolish the procedure for formulating deductions of reserve requirements in the national currency for deposits of commercial banks in foreign currencies; secondly, the reserve requirement rate for deposits in foreign currencies should be set at the level of the required reserve ratio (4%) for deposits in the national currency and the amount of reserve requirements should not be deducted from the banks’ Nostro correspondent account. As a result, the balance of funds in the correspondent accounts of commercial banks “Nostro” will increase and the resource base will be strengthened.

2. Taking into consideration the facts of limited ability of commercial banks to attract time deposits, increase in payments through current accounts of businesses

⁴ The table is compiled by the author on the basis of statistics of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
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(loans and budget loans are issued to finance current expenditures of enterprises) and high share of cash in the M1 monetary aggregate under conditions of the coronavirus pandemic, it is necessary to change the monetary policy indicator and make the monetary aggregate M1 the object of control by the Central Bank.

As of January 1, 2022, the share of cash in the monetary aggregate M1 in the country amounted to 46.1%⁵. This is a relatively high level. In Russia, for example, as of January 1, 2022, the share of cash in the monetary aggregate M1 accounted for 37.4%⁶.

In general, a sharp growth in the amount of cash and an increase in the share of cash in the money supply necessitate maintaining control over the monetary aggregate M1. For example, the use of the monetary aggregate M1 by the US Federal Reserve as an indicator of monetary policy in the 1990s is justified by the increase in the share of cash in this monetary aggregate: “In the USA, the importance of cash as money and as a component of the M1 monetary aggregate has increased. For example, in 1973, the United States had 325 USD per capita in cash, but by 1993 that figure had risen and reached 1050 USD. The share of cash in the M1 monetary aggregate rose from 20.5 percent in late 1960 to more than 30 percent in late 1992”.⁷

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⁵ Monetary statistics //www.cbu.uz

⁶ Money supply//www.cbr.ru

⁷ Miller L.R., Van Hoose D.D. Modern money and banking. Translated from English. – Moscow: Infra-M, 2000. – p. 50.

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